

Social and Pedagogical Need for Forming Creative Thinking Skills in Students

Akbarov B. A.

Associate Professor, Head of the Department of Social Sciences, Namangan Engineering and Construction Institute

Sh. T. Makhmudov

Researcher, Namangan Engineering and Construction Institute

Abstract. *In this article, students can develop creative thinking skills, creative thinking skills that help them make confident decisions and quickly acquire new knowledge for success, improve people's lives through new ideas, connect people and opportunities, or there is talk of harmonizing.*

Key words: *Creativity, creative thinking, new technology, skills, innovation, advanced thinking.*

Introduction

Creativity and achievements have advanced human civilization worldwide in a variety of fields, from science and technology to philosophy, arts, and humanities. So, creative thinking is more than just generating random ideas. It is a real skill, based on knowledge and experience, that enables a person to achieve better results in sometimes difficult conditions. Societies and organizations around the world increasingly need innovative knowledge and creativity to solve the problems of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, which in turn increases the importance of innovation and creative thinking, which is teamwork [1]. The main goal of education is to develop the skills that a student will need today and in the future to successfully live in society. Creative thinking is an important skill for today's youth. These skills help them adapt to a world that is constantly and rapidly changing, requiring workers to have "21st century" skills that go beyond basic literacy. In general, today's student is expected to work in areas that do not even exist today, to solve new problems using new technologies. Developing creative thinking skills in students enables them to solve increasingly complex local and global problems in an innovative way[2].

In addition, creative thinking helps students interpret events, experiences and behaviour in new and personally meaningful ways.

supports through The student's imagination and curiosity play a role in the learning process: creative thinking thus becomes a means of mutual agreement, even in the context of predetermined educational goals. In order to increase students' motivation and interest in school, it is necessary to introduce new forms of teaching that take into account the creativity and enthusiasm of all students. This can especially help students who are not interested in the learning process, helping them to express their opinions and realize their potential[3].

Like any other skill, creative thinking can be developed through a practical approach. Some teachers may feel that developing students' creative thinking comes at the expense of other subjects in the curriculum. In fact, students can think creatively in all subjects. Creative thinking can be developed through approaches that support exploration and invention rather than blind memorization during

class time. Teachers need to be able to recognize creative thinking, know the conditions that are conducive to such thinking, and know how to help students think more creatively. A better understanding of how creative thinking occurs, in turn, helps teachers understand that students' creative ideas need a certain amount of time to "incubate" during the educational process [4].

Today, creativity and innovation are often cited as key skills for success in careers and life around the world. Innovation is a decisive force for the effectiveness of an organization's performance and survival in the marketplace. Changes in technology, globalization, and increased competition create an environment in which creativity and innovation are needed to cope with situational and economic pressures and frequent changes. Therefore, designers and developers of organizational systems must innovate almost constantly to adapt the organization to such changes [5].

Research interest in creativity is evident in a number of disciplines, most notably in psychology, business studies, and cognitive science. However, it can also be found in education, humanities and theology, social sciences, engineering, technology and mathematics.

These disciplines cover the relationship between creativity and general intelligence, personality type, mental and spiritual processes, mental health and artificial intelligence. The potential for developing creativity through education, training, leadership and organizational practices, the determinants of how creativity is valued and perceived, the development of creativity in the national economic interest and the use of creative resources to improve the effectiveness of teaching and learning.

Creativity is the skill of imaginative thinking, creative thinking. All successful people in the world, from businessmen to artists, have distinguished themselves by this skill. Creativity means an unconventional, original idea of something that is not yet understood. For example, when the artist and sculptor Michelangelo was asked how he created his works so beautifully and flawlessly, he replied: "Every time I enter into the creative process, I see characters trapped in a huge marble, and I want to free them. I want to." Creative thinking develops ideas, and ideas inspire change. Creative thinking means improving people's lives through new ideas, connecting people and possibilities, that is, bringing them into harmony.

Summary. If you ask successful people about the secret of their success, they will tell you that they simply focused on something that others did not do. In fact, they were able to consolidate their accumulated experience and combine knowledge. They focused on failures more than others. The only difference between leaders in their field and those who follow them is innovation, that is, foresight. It is impossible to innovate without failing. Creativity is thinking of new ideas, innovation is implementing advanced work. To do this, you must not be afraid of failure.

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